

DAMAGE MONITORING OF SANDWICH PANELS BASED ON IMPACT FORCE IDENTIFICATION USING RADIATED SOUNDS

Satoshi Atobe¹, Masato Muramoto² and Hisao Fukunaga³

¹Department of Aerospace Engineering, Tohoku University
6-6-01 Aramaki-aza-Aoba, Aoba-ku, Sendai 980-8579, Japan
Email: atobe@ssl.mech.tohoku.ac.jp

²Graduate School of Engineering, Tohoku University
6-6-01 Aramaki-aza-Aoba, Aoba-ku, Sendai 980-8579, Japan
Email: muramoto@ssl.mech.tohoku.ac.jp

³Department of Aerospace Engineering, Tohoku University
6-6-01 Aramaki-aza-Aoba, Aoba-ku, Sendai 980-8579, Japan
Email: fukunaga@ssl.mech.tohoku.ac.jp

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a method for identifying impact forces acting on sandwich panels, and also detecting the impact-induced damage using the information obtained by the impact force identification. In this study, the radiated sound from the impacted panel is measured with microphones, and the measured data are used to identify the impact location and the force history. The impact location is identified using the differences in the arrival times of the sound wave at the microphones. The force history is determined from the measured sound pressure using the identification method based on experimental transfer matrices. The occurrence of damage at the impacted location is judged by examining the identified force history for the presence of sharp drops and fluctuations due to damage propagation. The validity of the impact force identification and damage detection is demonstrated with a sandwich panel composed of CFRP facesheets and an aramid honeycomb core. In the experiments, the impact force is applied with an impulse hammer. The results reveal that, even when damages are induced by the applied impact, the location and force history of the impact can be identified accurately by using the radiated sound. Moreover, it is shown that the occurrence and location of the damage can be estimated in real time from the identified impact force.

1 INTRODUCTION

Over the past few decades, honeycomb sandwich structures have been extensively used in aircrafts and ships/boats due to their advantageous properties such as high specific strength and high specific stiffness [1]. On the other hand, the disadvantage in tolerance to low-velocity impacts could limit the application of sandwich structures. When a foreign object impact event occurs, sandwich structures suffer from impact damages which degrade the mechanical properties of the structure. Moreover, the induced damage is barely visible and difficult to detect by visual inspection. Therefore, various studies on the effects of low-velocity impacts on sandwich structures have been conducted thus far by many researchers [2]. In recent years, a variety of techniques for monitoring the structural integrity automatically and in real time using the data provided from a built-in sensor network are being developed to enhance the reliability and ensure the safety of various structures. The application of such structural health monitoring (SHM) techniques to honeycomb sandwich structures has also been examined [3-11].

Minakuchi et al. [3] and Okabe et al. [4] reported methods for detecting disbonds and impact damages in a sandwich panel composed of CFRP facesheets and an aluminum honeycomb core. In their studies, damage detection was performed by monitoring the reflection spectrum of optical fiber sensors which were embedded in between the facesheet and the core. Subsequently, they also proposed a method for identifying the location and size of the damage [5].

Damage detection of sandwich panels has also been carried out by utilizing the wave propagation in structures. In most studies, elastic waves (e.g. Lamb waves) are generated and received with surface mounted piezoelectric actuators/sensors, and the sensor responses are analyzed to detect damages such as disbonds between the facesheet and the core. For example, in the work done by Kessler et al. [6], the disbond was detected by comparing the measured sensor responses with a baseline data which was preliminarily acquired from an intact structure. In another study [7], the location of the disbond was identified using the arrival time of the wave reflected from the damage to the sensor. Moreover, estimation of the disbond size [8] has been attempted using the amplitude of the wave received by the sensor. Song et al. [9] verified that, when a disbond exists in the propagation path of the elastic wave, an increase in the amplitude of the sensor response can be seen because the leaking of the waves from the facesheet into the core is impeded by the disbond. Based on this wave propagation characteristic, they proposed a method for identifying the locations and sizes of multiple disbonds, and also revealed the validity of their method experimentally with a sandwich panel composed of aluminum facesheets and an aramid honeycomb core. Mustapha et al. [10] proposed a method for identifying the damage location based on the time reversal method. Without using any baseline data from an intact structure, they demonstrated the detection of a debonding in a CFRP facesheets/aramid honeycomb core sandwich panel by comparing the actuator input and the reconstructed signal after time reversal.

Application of acoustic emission (AE) techniques to SHM was investigated by Leone Jr. et al. [11]. In their study, loading tests of notched full-scale honeycomb sandwich composite fuselage panels were conducted under various conditions, and the initiation and progression of notch tip damage were monitored using the measured AE data. Here, the locations and the intensities of the AE events were correlated with the strain fields measured with a digital image correlation system in order to verify the potential of AE techniques for SHM application.

For the detection of impact damages, SHM techniques based on impact force identification are also promising. Identification of the impact location and force history can provide significant information useful for estimating the extent and location of the impact-induced damage. Thus far, application of impact force identification to damage detection has been examined with CFRP laminated plates [12] and FRP pressure vessels [13]. As to honeycomb sandwich structures, the relationship between the impact damage and the force history has been examined in detail by experiments [14, 15], and methods for identifying the impact location [16, 17] and the force history [18, 19] have been proposed. However, these previous studies on impact force identification did not deal with fatal impacts which induce damages to the structure. Thus, the validity of applying impact force identification to damage detection has not been verified for sandwich structures.

The aim of this paper is to establish a technique for detecting damages induced in sandwich structures by low-velocity impacts. Identification of impact forces acting on honeycomb sandwich panels is examined in conjunction with the utilization of the identified impact force for estimating the occurrence and location of impact damage. The impact location and the force history are identified by employing the identification method based on experimental transfer matrices [20], which can be applied without constructing an analytical model of the structure. Here, the data used for identifying the impact force are the radiated sound from the impacted structure which is measured with microphones [20, 21]. Impact tests are conducted with an impulse hammer to verify the validity of estimating the occurrence and location of the impact-induced damage based on the identification results of the impact location and force history.

2 METHOD FOR IDENTIFYING THE IMPACT FORCE USING RADIATED SOUNDS

In this chapter, the experimental method [20] adopted for the identification of the impact force acting on the sandwich panel is described. The sound waves generated by the low-velocity impact event are measured with microphones, and the acquired data are used to identify the location and force history of the applied impact. Unlike sensors which must be bonded or embedded, e.g. piezoelectric sensors and optical fiber sensors, microphones will not deteriorate the structure since they are non-contact sensors. In addition, the use of the radiated sounds will facilitate the impact location identification because unlike the velocities of elastic waves in anisotropic solids, the velocity of sound in air does not depend on the frequency nor on the propagation direction. The identified impact location and force history are used to estimate the occurrence and location of damage. Note that, the damages dealt in the present study

Figure 1: CFRP sandwich panel subjected to impact.

Figure 2: Construction of experimental transfer matrix.

are barely visible impact damages which will not significantly degrade the mechanical properties of the panel such as the bending stiffness.

2.1 Construction of experimental transfer matrices

Figure 1 depicts a sandwich panel subjected to a transverse impact force. A Cartesian coordinate system (x, y, z) , whose origin is placed at the center of the upper surface of the panel, is adopted. The impact force is supposed to act at $(x_F, y_F, 0)$, and the sound which radiated from the bottom surface of the impacted panel is measured with microphones placed at a total of I locations. The force history \mathbf{f} and the time history of sound pressure \mathbf{p}_i , which is measured by the i -th microphone placed at (x_{Si}, y_{Si}, z_{Si}) , can be related by:

$$\mathbf{p}_i = G_i(x_F, y_F, x_{Si}, y_{Si}, z_{Si}) \mathbf{f} \quad (1)$$

where

$$\mathbf{p}_i = \begin{Bmatrix} p_i(t_1) \\ p_i(t_2) \\ \vdots \\ p_i(t_N) \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{f} = \begin{Bmatrix} f(t_1) \\ f(t_2) \\ \vdots \\ f(t_N) \end{Bmatrix}, \quad G_i(x_F, y_F, x_{Si}, y_{Si}, z_{Si}) = \begin{bmatrix} g_{i,1} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ g_{i,2} & g_{i,1} & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & 0 \\ g_{i,N} & g_{i,N-1} & \cdots & g_{i,1} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

Here, the force $f(t)$ and sound pressure $p_i(t)$ are sampled at intervals of Δt_s , and therefore $t_n = n\Delta t_s$ ($n=1, \dots, N$). $G_i(x_F, y_F, x_{Si}, y_{Si}, z_{Si})$ is a transfer matrix which is composed of the Green's function. Note that the transfer matrix is defined by a function of the impact location (x_F, y_F) and the sensor location (x_{Si}, y_{Si}, z_{Si}) , but it is not dependent on the force history $f(t)$.

In the present method, the transfer matrix is necessary for identifying the force history. Thus, the components of G_i are determined experimentally in order to construct an experimental transfer matrix. As can be seen from Eq. (2), the transfer matrix can be constructed with the N components in its first column. By rearranging Eq. (1), we obtain:

$$\mathbf{p}_i = F \mathbf{g}_i \quad (3)$$

where

$$\mathbf{g}_i = \begin{Bmatrix} g_{i,1} \\ g_{i,2} \\ \vdots \\ g_{i,N} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad F = \begin{bmatrix} f(t_1) & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ f(t_2) & f(t_1) & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & 0 \\ f(t_N) & f(t_{N-1}) & \cdots & f(t_1) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

Preliminary impact tests are conducted with an impulse hammer without damaging the structure, and the components of the transfer matrix are determined by solving the following least-squares problem using the measured sensor responses and force histories.

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{minimize : } \sum_{k=1}^K \|\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_i^k - \tilde{F}^k \mathbf{g}_i\|^2 \\ &\text{variables : } \mathbf{g}_i \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Henceforth, variables with a tilde ($\tilde{\cdot}$) will denote measured variables. To construct an adequate transfer matrix by reducing the effect of measurement error, the experimental data for determining g_i are acquired by conducting impact tests K times.

As previously noted, the transfer matrix is defined by a function of the impact location (x_F, y_F) , and it also differs between each sensor. Since multiple microphones are used to identify an unpredictable impact force, the experimental transfer matrix must be determined for each sensor and for an arbitrary impact location. Therefore, as shown in Fig. 2, the identification region is divided into some discrete grid areas and preliminary impact tests are conducted at every grid node. Then, the experimental transfer matrices are constructed for each set relating one node (impact location) to one sensor location (microphone) by employing Eq. (5). Inside each grid area, the transfer matrices are determined by an interpolation operation with shape functions of a four-node two-dimensional element which is commonly used in finite element analyses.

2.2 Impact location identification and force history identification

When the structure is subjected to an unknown impact force, the impact location (x_F, y_F) is identified first using the arrival times of the sound waves at the microphones. The difference in arrival times for the i -th and j -th microphones can be expressed as:

$$\Delta T_{ij} = T_j - T_i = \frac{r_j}{v} - \frac{r_i}{v} \quad (6)$$

where, T is the arrival time of the sound wave, r is the distance between the impact location and sensor, and v is the speed of sound. The impact location is determined by the point where the deviation between the differences in arrival times given by Eq. (6) and the differences calculated from the measured arrival times becomes the minimum:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{minimize : } & \sum_{i=1}^{I-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^I \left\{ \Delta \tilde{T}_{ij} - \left(\frac{r_j}{v} - \frac{r_i}{v} \right) \right\}^2 \\ \text{variables : } & x_F, y_F \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

In this study, the conjugate gradient method with the golden section search method is used to solve Eq. (7). The measured arrival time is defined as the time at which the measured sound pressure crosses over a preset threshold. The speed of sound is determined by substituting the measured room temperature T_{air} (in Celsius) into the following equation:

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma R}{M} (T_{\text{air}} + 273.15)} \quad (8)$$

where γ is the specific heat ratio, R is the gas constant, and M is the molar mass.

After the impact location is identified, the force history is identified by adjusting the sound pressures calculated by Eq. (1) with the preliminarily-constructed experimental transfer matrices to the sound pressures measured at impact. Then, the identification problem reduces to a minimization problem that is formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{minimize : } & \sum_{i=1}^I \| \tilde{p}_i - G_i(x_F, y_F, x_{Si}, y_{Si}, z_{Si}) f \|^2 \\ \text{subject to : } & f(t) \geq 0 \\ \text{variables : } & f \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Here, the constraint is adopted because the impact force is assumed to act in the compression direction. To solve Eq. (9), the quadratic programming method is used.

In the present study, it is assumed that the damages induced by the impact will not affect the transfer matrices G_i which are used in Eq. (9) to identify the force history. This assumption is considered to be valid when the extent of the damage is small, and it will be verified by the experimental results shown in Chapter 4.

3 EXPERIMENT OF IMPACT FORCE IDENTIFICATION AND DAMAGE DETECTION

Figure 3 depicts the specimen used in the experiment. A sandwich panel, which consists of CFRP facesheets and an aramid honeycomb core, was manufactured by Showa Aircraft Industry. The facesheets (0.5 mm thick) were made with woven prepreps, and then bonded to the core (cell size 3.2 mm, 15 mm thick) with film adhesives. As shown in the figure, two edges of the panel were clamped with 50 mm-wide jigs.

A schematic of the experimental setup is illustrated in Fig. 4. The impact force is applied to the panel with an impulse hammer (Ono Sokki, GK-1200), and the radiated sound is measured with microphones (Ono Sokki, MI-1234) at eight locations indicated in Table 1. The signals from the microphones are amplified by a preamplifier and a sensor amplifier (Ono Sokki, MI-3111 and SR-2200), and then recorded at 5 μ s intervals with a data logger (Keyence, NR-500). Simultaneously, the force obtained from the impulse hammer is also measured for the purpose of constructing the experimental transfer matrices and for assessing the identified force history.

The identification region is a 320 mm \times 200 mm rectangular region whose center coincides with that of the panel, as shown in Fig. 3. The region is divided into 20 mm squares, and the experimental transfer matrices are constructed at the locations of the 187 grid nodes. For each grid node, preliminarily impact tests are conducted five times with an impulse hammer instrumented with a hard tip made of plastic, and the experimental transfer matrices were determined using the acquired data and Eq. (5). The time intervals for the force history identification is set $\Delta t_s = 20 \mu$ s. The speed of sound for the impact location identification was determined by substituting the room temperature $T_{\text{air}} = 26.0^\circ\text{C}$ measured with a thermo-hygrometer (Lufft, E200) into Eq. (8). In performing the impact force identification by Eqs. (7) and (9), only the data obtained by four microphones, which are selected in the order of the arrival time of the sound wave, are used so as to omit the data obtained by microphones distant from the impact location.

To verify the validity of the present method, first, impact force identification and damage detection are demonstrated with the same impulse hammer which was used in the preliminarily impact tests for constructing the experimental transfer matrices. Then, experiments are also conducted using a different impulse hammer (Dytran, 5850B), which can be instrumented with a soft polyurethane impact tip and a hammer head extender, to reveal that the validity of the present method does not depend on the stiffness or the mass of the impactor.

Figure 3: Schematic of specimen.

Figure 4: Experimental setup.

Table 1: Locations of microphones.

Microphone 1 (-150, -60, -96)	Microphone 2 (-50, -60, -96)	Microphone 3 (50, -60, -96)	Microphone 4 (150, -60, -96)
Microphone 5 (-150, 60, -96)	Microphone 6 (-50, 60, -96)	Microphone 7 (50, 60, -96)	Microphone 8 (150, 60, -96)

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First, impact force identification was performed for the impact tests which were conducted without damaging the sandwich panel. Then, impacts were applied so as to induce damages within the panel, and the impact forces were identified using the acquired data. The identification was performed at ten locations for the undamaged case, and also the same for the damaged case. Here, the impulse hammer instrumented with the hard tip was used to apply the impacts. After each test, the impact point was checked for impact-induced damages by visual and tactile inspections. In addition, the measured force history was also examined to check the signs of damage occurrence, such as sharp load drops and fluctuations.

Figure 5 shows the impact locations identified using the difference in the arrival time of the impact-induced sound wave between the microphones. In the figure, \otimes and \odot depict the measured impact location and the identified location respectively, and the corresponding markers are enclosed by an ellipse. In the case of the ten undamaged cases, the distance between the measured impact location and the identified one was 12.6 mm at most, and 6.6 mm on average. As to the damaged cases, the maximum error and the average error of the identified impact locations were 11.9 mm and 6.0 mm, respectively. The results reveal that the accuracy of the identified impact locations does not differ depending on the damage occurrence. Even when damages are induced within the sandwich panel by the impact, the first sound wave which reaches the microphone is the radiated sound due to the elastic deformation of the panel before the damage initiation. Since the present method for impact location identification uses only the information on the arrival times of the sound wave at the microphones, the location of the impact can be identified with sufficient accuracy regardless of the damage occurrence. Thus, the damage location could also be estimated accurately based on the identification result of the impact location.

The force history identification and the detection of damage occurrence will be discussed by focusing on four tests results, i.e. one undamaged case A and three damaged cases B*, C* and D* indicated in Fig. 5. Figure 6 shows the images of the impacted locations and the measured force histories and sound pressures acquired in the four cases. In the case of point B* shown in Fig. 6(b), a 4 mm-long crack was induced in the upper facesheet by the impact. In contrast to the smooth force history shown in Fig. 6(a) which was measured in the undamaged case A, fine fluctuations and sharp load drops can be seen in the measured force history for case B*. The fine fluctuations are associated with the initiation/progression of delaminations and matrix cracks in the facesheets, while the sharp load drops are caused by the degradation of the local stiffness due to core bulking and facesheet penetration [14,15]. As to the measured sound pressure, only a slight difference in the high-frequency components can be seen between the two cases A and B*. Figure 6(c) shows the test result for case C* in which a hole with a 4 mm diameter and 1 mm depth was induced by the applied impact. The penetration of the upper facesheet caused the sharp load drop which occurred when the force reached 400 N, and the flat force history seen after the load drop is due to the temporary recovery of the local stiffness associated with core crushing. In the case of

Figure 5: Identification results of impact location.

(a) Point A: No damage

(b) Point B*: Top facesheet fracture

(c) Point C*: Top facesheet penetration and core crushing

(d) Point D*: Dent

Figure 6: Image of impacted point with the measured force history and sound pressure.

Figure 7: Identification results of force history.

point C*, fluctuations can also be seen in the measured sound pressure at about $t=0.7$ ms. Case D* shown in Fig. 6(d) is a typical example of a damaged case in which a barely visible impact damage was induced. Although no damage was detected visually, a dent was confirmed by the tactile inspection. The damage occurrence can also be inferred from the fluctuations and load drops seen in the measured force history. On the other hand, no signs of damage occurrence can be confirmed from the measured sound pressure. As can be seen from Fig. 6, regardless of the type of the impact-induced damage, the signs of damage occurrence appear distinctly in the force history but not in the sound pressure. Thus, if it is possible to accurately identify the force history using the measured sound pressures, the shape of the identified force history can be used to judge the occurrence of impact damages.

Figure 7 shows the results of force history identification for the four cases presented in Fig. 6. In the case of the undamaged case A, the identified force history agrees well with the measured one, and its shape is smooth. The identification results for the damaged cases B*, C* and D* are also in good agreement with the measured force histories, and the signs of damage occurrence can be seen in all of the identified force histories. Even though the signs of impact damages may not appear distinctly in the measured sound pressures, the force history can be identified accurately regardless of the damage occurrence. As previously noted in Chapter 2, the experimental transfer matrices used to identify the force history in this study are constructed based on the measured data from impact tests conducted without damaging the structure. Thus, the identified force histories for cases B*, C* and D* are those obtained without considering the change in the structural integrity. The effects of the impact-induced damages can be neglected because the damages dealt in the present study are those that do not significantly degrade the bending stiffness of the panel. The results verify the validity of detecting the impact damage by examining the shape of the identified force history.

In the case of a foreign object impact event, the stiffness and the mass of the impactor are also unknown. Therefore, the validity of the present method was also examined by changing the stiffness and the mass of the impactor. Here, the stiffness was changed by using two impact tips: a hard tip made of plastic and a soft tip made of polyurethane. And the mass was changed by attaching a hammer head

Table 2: Results of location identification for impacts applied by changing the stiffness and mass of the impactor.

Case	Measured location (x_F, y_F) in mm	Identified location (x_{ID}, y_{ID}) in mm	Error (mm)
Soft tip	(115, -63)	(117.0, -57.6)	5.8
Hard tip with extender mass	(-7, 67)	(-5.0, -57.3)	9.9
Soft tip with extender mass	(140, -20)	(141.8, -9.1)	11.1

Figure 8: Results of force history identification for impacts applied by changing the stiffness and mass of the impactor.

extender. Note that the impulse hammer used here is not identical to the one used for constructing the experimental transfer matrices. The identification results of the impact location and the force history are shown in Table 2 and Fig. 8, respectively. In the case of the present three tests, a dent like the one confirmed in case D* was induced by the impact. As can be seen from the table, the accuracy of the identified impact location is not dependent on the stiffness or the mass of the impactor. In addition, the force histories are also identified with sufficient accuracy, and the signs of the damage occurrence can be confirmed. The experimental results reveal that the present method can be applied to sandwich structures for the identification of the impact forces and the detection of the impact-induced damages associated with foreign object impact events.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a method for identifying the impact forces acting on sandwich panels using the sound measured at impact has been proposed along with a method for detecting the occurrence and location of impact-induced damages based on the identified impact forces. The validity of the proposed method was examined experimentally by conducting impact tests using a CFRP facesheets/aramid honeycomb core sandwich panel and an impulse hammer as the specimen and impactor, respectively. The knowledge obtained from the experimental results is summarized as follows:

- Regardless of the damage occurrence, the impact location can be identified accurately using the difference in the arrival time of the sound wave between the microphones. Therefore, the damage location can also be estimated accurately from the identified impact location.
- When the impact-induced damages do not significantly degrade the bending stiffness of the panel, the force history can be identified with sufficient accuracy using the identification method based on experimental transfer matrices.
- The occurrence of impact damage can be judged by examining the identified force history for the presence of fluctuations and sharp load drop which are confirmed only when the panel is damaged by the impact event.

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